

Impact of Fine Arts Curriculum on the Academic Motivation, Academic, Self-Efficacy and Self-Regulation

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Abstract

The curriculum has a key role in developing the student's motivation and self-efficacy. But evidence on the examination of fine arts curricula are not sufficient, particularly on individual self-determination. The current research tries to address the above issue by proposing a comprehensive framework on fine arts curriculum and students 'academic self-efficacy, academic self-regulated, academic motivation. The three concepts academic motivation, self-efficacy, and self-regulation were extracted based on the theory of self-determination, and the theory of goal orientation. The current research gives insight to future researchers to assess the role of fine arts in shaping the cognitive psychology of individuals.

Keywords: Academic Motivation, Self-regulation, Self-Efficacy, Fine Arts Curriculum

Introduction

Individuals from different regions must create relationships despite their differences in customs and culture as a result of globalisation (Davis et al., 2020; Inman & Turner, 2007). It is essential for individuals from different countries to understand one other and their customs and values. Arts education is a great approach to learning about this subject (Kallio & Länsman, 2018). People may learn to deal with and embrace difference, to express their feelings, and to distinguish between different kinds of values by pursuing an education in the arts. Arts education enables schools to teach children about ethics, the realities of the world, and their rights and duties via the lens of the arts. In addition, the study of the arts fosters students' sense of self-worth, self-confidence, and self-regulation (Kallio & Länsman, 2018).

Winner, Goldstein, and Vincent-Lancrin (2013) summarised the many ways in which arts education helps students. Learning the arts can help students develop their imagination and creativity, allow them to express themselves, assist in their understanding of core subjects, aid in their observation of the world around them, assist them in making decisions, and help them develop values like concentration and persistence. These are just a few examples of the benefits of arts education.

The arts must be considered an essential element of education. They are tools for living life reflectively, joyfully and with the ability to shape the future.” The fine arts include music, theatre, drawing, painting, or sculpture and have been in education curriculum since the 19th century and have been shown to have a great impact on students. Unfortunately, to schools, the fine arts are not considered the “money-maker,” but instead sports. After the Great Recession, many schools had budget cuts, and their art programs were the first to go with the belief that the loss of the arts wouldn’t be as crucial. There are many benefits to having fine arts classes in school, as Plato and others who have studied education have emphasized the importance of art in education. Having fine art classes within the entirety of the education system is essential to making us as humans complete.

According to Ochshorn (2016), students that are exposed to the arts are more successful. Learning abilities, school attendance, critical thinking and creativity were all said to be boosted by it. Understanding how the arts influence people's thoughts and their lives is essential to an effective arts education. Art's significance is incalculable and countless. This means that the approaches are ways of learning and investigating, responding and revealing / demonstration / imagination / depicting / making meaning. In school and in the minds and hearts of lifelong learners, they are a vital part of the educational experience.

Students' perceptions of the fine arts in terms of academic self-efficacy, motivation, and self-regulation are critical to this investigation (Razzoqovna, 2019). Study participants' opinions of fine arts curriculum as a predictor for academic success will be examined. Visual arts are often incorporated into other subject areas by teachers. From the beginning, arts education has had a favourable impact on student learning. Analysis of relevant study literature found that students' behaviour, engagement, creativity, and academic achievement are all favourably impacted by images.

Throughout time, education has been viewed as a lifelong process of learning and adjustment. One of the aims of education in the 21st century is to open new doors so that the skills and standards relevant to the Digital Age learners may be accessed. Higher-order thinking, creativity, critical thinking, communication, and teamwork are all part of this. In accordance with this, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) aims to consistently improve the quality of Higher Education by ensuring that its programmes and system meet worldwide standards (Quitoras & Abuso, 2021). The Commission on Higher Education Research advises higher education institutions' faculties to do research in accordance with the Commission's objectives. This study's objective is to determine whether or not visual arts can be effectively used to educate humanities (also known as "Art Appreciation") in schools. In Saudi universities, there are few research on academic self-efficacy in the field of fine arts (Koura & Al-Hebaishi, 2014). The fine arts curriculum in Saudi universities is not standardised. The curriculum at each institution is determined by the department's recommendations. Prior studies have argued that further study is needed to better understand the differences amongst fine art departments (Al-Senan, Al-Isa, & Al-Sultan, 2018). However, little emphasis has been made to the influence of the fine arts curriculum on academic self-efficacy, academic self-regulation, and academic motivation.

Hence, the current research will try to address the above issue by proposing a comprehensive framework on fine arts curriculum and students' academic self-efficacy, academic self-regulated, academic motivation.

Literature Review

The study of the arts is an important component of a person's growth in today's society, and it is taught in many schools. Since Plato, it is thought that those who have studied art as a topic and devoted themselves to it have acknowledged its importance in today's educational process (Nettleship, 1897). Every human being's existence is enriched by the inclusion of arts education in their educational curriculum, no matter where they live. Among the many goals of the arts curriculum are those that help students succeed in a wide range of professions. Some of these goals include developing critical thinking, creativity, and communication skills, cultivating artistic compassion skills, creating a higher degree of cultural awareness, and cultivating positive cultures and behavioural attitudes in the students (Al_Dabbagh, 2020). In addition to this, the fundamental goals of the arts curriculum are to increase people's happiness and satisfaction in various arts activities, and to encourage them to pursue a long-term interest in this topic, i.e., arts education.

"Arts have long been recognised part of the human emotive experience and required by the young people as a medium for safe expression, communication, discovery, imagination, cultural and historical awareness" (Finley, Messinger, & Mazur, 2020). It is essential for individuals of any country to understand one other's customs, traditions, and values. Since arts education may help students gain this awareness, it should be considered an option (Punzalan, 2018). Individuals in today's environment may be better able to embrace diversity, express feelings, and recognise principles with the support of arts education, according to Punzalan (2018). It also helps educational institutions like schools throughout the world to give a greater grasp of ethics to their pupils and encourages the students to picture community realities, so they may better comprehend their own rights and duties as well as the rights of others (Punzalan, 2018). It has been noted by Latta, Hanson, Ragoonaden, Briggs, and Middleton (2017) that the range of artistic disciplines goes much beyond the traditional categories of dance, music, and theatre.

Aside from providing students with the opportunity to experience and create information, arts education also helps students develop problem-solving and respect for others abilities (Latta et al., 2017). Because of this, it is clear that the introduction of arts topics in the current education system has inherent value in enhancing student-teacher communication and developing shared meanings (Latta et al., 2017). According to Mahgoub and Aldbesi (2016), it can be concluded that arts subjects have a crucial part in creating human experiences, as these have promoted transformation within individuals and societies by reflecting any perspective and reacting well to any situation. It is critical for the growth and advancement of creative citizens that an efficient arts education system and its systematic implementation be in place (Mahgoub & Aldbesi, 2016). Arts-related disciplines and their implementation in diverse schools, colleges, and universities may therefore be claimed to have a direct and strong relationship between students and the many cultures, traditions, and histories that make up the present educational

system. As a result of this relationship, students are able to develop a better knowledge of the unique viewpoints and beliefs of the global community (Mahgoub & Aldbesi, 2016). Despite the creative advances in modern learning and teaching methods brought about by digital learning, many schools throughout the world still rely on text-books for arts and other courses. In the end, this demonstrates the need and importance of including the arts into today's educational system.

Arts Subject in Saudi Arabia

One of the most prominent Islamic countries is Saudi Arabia, known as the Bride of the Red Sea. Therefore in research, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) has a wide range of economic opportunities that may be quantified in the form of increased global commerce, large-scale investments in various industrial or company segments, and projected developments at various commercial locations (Arcadis, 2019). There are a number of functional and well-functioning bodies in the cities of Saudi Arabia, such as: The Consultative Council, The Principal Ruling System, The Shura Council and Regional Law, which all have a significant impact on the country's political landscape (Jeddah Economic Gateway, 2017, p. 6). A large portion of Saudi Arabia's budget is dedicated to education, as well as to training for teachers and other workers. For example, in 2017, the Saudi government committed 22% of total budget expenditures to improving the education system in the country (Jeddah Economic Gateway, 2017).

According to Art Jameel's LLC (2019) report, the Saudi Arabian Ministry of Education collaborated with Art Jameel to create and implement numerous pilot programmes for art instructors and students between 2013 and 2015. In Saudi Arabia during the year of 2017-2018, a number of modules were introduced for art lessons aimed at both students and teachers. Some of the most successful training courses and artistic traditions were found in these modules (Art Jameel, 2019).

Theoretical Framework Development

Motivational theories, such as goal orientation theory Ames (1992) and self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000), prescribe the ideal learning situation: educators should aim to make their courses attractive or fascinating in order to encourage students. Extrinsic and intrinsic motivation are analogous to the self-determination theory's concepts of learning and performance motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). It is important to understand the difference between intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation in order to understand the difference between these two types of motivation. While in self-determination theory, students' motivations for learning and performance are emphasised, we only consider their motivations for learning and performance. Because of this, the three concepts academic motivation, self-efficacy, and self-regulation are very similar to the concepts intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in the theory of self-determination, and mastery and performance goals in the theory of goal orientation (Ryan and Deci, 2000). (Ames, 1992). These theories, on the other hand, quantify motivation by asking students why they want to study and perform.

Therefore, the current study examines the impact of fine arts curriculum on academic motivation, academic self-efficacy and academic self-regulation. Figure below shows the framework of the study

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework of the study

Academic Motivation

Using Bandura (1977) social cognitive theory and its connection to self-efficacy and agency, the wider subject of academic motivation in student performance is raised. Motivation, according to social cognitive theory, influences both learning and academic achievement (Bandura, 1997). However, motivation isn't a must for learning. Students, on the other hand, may not perform well academically if their motivators are weak or absent from the classroom (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2014). Researchers in higher education are fascinated by the complexities of the topic of academic motivation. "Performance," "persistence," and "curiosity" are some of the phrases used by researchers to describe the motivation for a person's actions. For college educators, figuring out how to motivate students to take on jobs that aren't intrinsically appealing is a top goal (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Students' behaviour and academic motivation were examined as a part of this study, with a focus on students' participation in peer-led learning aid support programmes, which may not be considered an appealing alternative when confronted with a learning difficulty. Consider if academic motivation is a learner attribute that can be measured, addressed and used in the academic setting.

Motivation is one of the most important sources of power that determines the direction, intensity and determination of student behavior in learning-teaching process. Motivation is both an attractive and a hindering subject. It is interesting because it is behind almost

everything a person does. Motivation has been widely studied in education and in other fields. Motivation is a complex psychological phenomenon; therefore, the absence of one major overarching definition or theory of motivation should not be surprising. Researchers have explored motivation from various theoretical perspectives, such as behavioral (Skinner, 1978), social (Bandura, 1997), cognitive, and humanistic standpoints. There are different levels (low to high) and types (intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation) of motivation. Intrinsic motivation refers to a desire to engage in a task derived from individual's interest or pure pleasure, whereas extrinsic motivation refers that individuals engage in tasks due to external reinforcements or rewards, such as wealth, power, fame, and popularity. Moreover, according to SDT, academic engagement is a manifestation of academic motivation in terms of participation in learning activities or academic tasks, which is influenced by to what extent students perceive that academic activities meet their psychological needs. Motivated, especially intrinsically, students tend to engage in such activities that satisfy their needs.

Academic Self-Efficacy

The concept of general SE was originally proposed by Bandura in his social cognitive theory. SE may be defined as an individual's belief in his or her ability to succeed in a specific situation or accomplish a specific task (e.g., Bandura, 1977, 1997, 2012). Although the concept of self-esteem is very similar, self-esteem involves an individual's emotional evaluation of own value. In contrast, SE comprises an individual's evaluation of own ability to achieve a goal or self-belief to do so. For example, in academic situation, it can be assumed that learners with high SE have higher motivation to learn, resulted in higher academic achievement, because those learners believe that they have an ability to achieve their goal. It is known that SE is influenced by gender, age, and domain. Huang (2012) conducted a meta-analysis and reported that ASE differs between gender, age, and also domains such as mathematics and social sciences.

From a theoretical perspective, SE can be strengthened through the experience of mastery, observing someone succeed, and social persuasion such as direct encouragement. In addition, physiological factors have been assumed to affect SE. For example, perceptions of pain, fatigue, and fear may have a marked, deleterious effect on SE. In a twin study, genetic factors explained 75% of the variation in SE (Waaktaar and Torgersen, 2013).

Social cognitive theory emphasises the importance of self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is influenced by both external and internal factors (Bandura, 1977). The concept of self-efficacy is based on the individual's assessment of external social circumstances. High self-efficacy, according to Bandura's (1977) theory, is more likely to perceive tough activities as something to master rather than something to avoid for those who feel they can do well. Academic self-efficacy can be developed in college by observing faculty and staff members and other students in the classroom as well as by engaging in behaviours that support learning and academic development, such as studying with others. According to Bandura (1977), a student's self-efficacy is a more accurate predictor of success than their actual ability. It appears that academic self-efficacy is the most important component in students achieving their academic goals, yet academic goals differ from student to student (Merritt & Buboltz, 2015). Students'

academic self-efficacy is a goal of higher education professionals, based on Bandura's social cognitive theory, because it increases the likelihood that the student will succeed.

To date, many previous studies have reported that a learner's ASE is strongly associated with academic outcomes (e.g., Robbins et al., 2004; Richardson et al., 2012; Honicke and Broadbent, 2016). The results have consistently revealed that higher scores of ASE are more likely to result in higher levels of academic performance. Furthermore, Robbins et al. (2004) demonstrated that achievement motivation affects academic performance. Richardson et al. (2012) found that grade goals and effort regulation are strong factors in academic performance, similar to ASE. Honicke and Broadbent (2016) noted that effort regulation, deep processing strategies, and goal orientation have moderated the relationship between ASE and academic performance. As noted, goal-related aspects, that is, grade goals and goal orientation, and effort regulation have been found by two of three meta-analyses to be the strongest factors that influence academic performance other than ASE. Furthermore, although only a paucity of longitudinal studies has been conducted on the relationship between ASE and academic variables, the most recent meta-analysis has revealed that a higher ASE enhances academic efficiency longitudinally and vice versa (Talsma et al., 2018). In contrast, some of the studies have revealed no significant relationship between ASE (e.g., Crippen et al., 2009; Cho and Shen, 2013; Ge ĳka, 2014). Operationalization of ASE, timing of measurement, and cultural differences have been proposed as reasons (Honicke and Broadbent, 2016). Currently, it has been assumed that ASE is one of the most important factors or predictors for learners to achieve learning success. This may mean that if a student's ASE is enhanced, the student may be able to achieve higher academic results.

Academic Self-Regulations

Because of the favourable effects it has on behaviour and the acquisition of knowledge, the capacity to self-regulate has long been considered a desirable trait (Reid, Harris, Graham, & Rock, 2012). Several studies have been done on the benefits of self-regulation in terms of behaviour and academic performance. "Self-Regulation refers to the self-directed process through which learners adapt their mental capacities into task-related capabilities." ' (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2001). To learn, students must have a technique or procedure they can rely on for managing and organising their thoughts and turning them into useful abilities. Setting goals and keeping track of progress toward them is one of the most important aspects of self-regulation. Becoming conscious of your own thoughts and motivations is essential for students who want to be self-regulated in their own education (Zimmerman, 2001).

Students' academic and behavioural outcomes benefit from self-regulation in the classroom. Students who might ordinarily be inactive in class can become active participants via the application of Self-Regulation strategies. Student learning has to be viewed as an activity that students engage in on their own, rather than as a passive outcome of instruction (Zimmerman, 2001). Making it easier for students to get involved in their education puts them in the driver's seat and gives them control.

Conclusion

Based on goal oriented theory and self-regulation theory, the current research tries to develop a conceptual model that can be examined in the KSA settings to evaluate the role of fine arts curriculum on students 'Academic motivation, self-efficacy, and self-regulation. It was noted that curriculum has key role in developing the student's motivation and self-efficacy. But evidences on the examination of fine arts curricula are not sufficient particularly on individual self-determination. The current research gives insight to the future researchers to assess the role of fine arts in shaping the cognitive psychology of the individuals.

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